

Earthquake Behaviour of Flat Slab Buildings – An Elastic Study

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Abstract Buildings are provided with flat slabs due to their versatility in interior design, architectural needs, rapidity in construction, and reduced storey height. But such buildings evidenced poor performance from past earthquakes sustaining brittle damages. Therefore, IS 1893-1 places restrictions on the design of a flat slab building with a response reduction factor of $R = 3$ considering (i) RC structural walls designed to resist entire lateral loads; (ii) perimeter RC special moment resisting frames designed to resist 25% lateral loads; and (if possible) an outrigger and belt truss system that connects the core structural wall and perimeter frames. Therefore, a set of RC buildings with different flat slab buildings is considered, and responses from equivalent static analysis (ESA) and model analyses are compared with conventional slab buildings. Response parameters considered include (i) the distribution of hogging and sagging moments in the slab under gravity and lateral loads; (ii) diaphragm flexibility; (iii) maximum interstorey drift; (iv) storey shear; (v) the modal mass participation ratio and natural period; and (vi) base shear. The bending moment in slabs increases in flat slab buildings under gravity loads and is reduced under lateral loads with the provision of structural walls. It is necessary to design flat slab buildings for huge forces, considering diaphragm action, and checking for diaphragm flexibility without including rigid diaphragms. The provision of perimeter beams with structural walls may increase the structural performance under inelastic actions, but it requires a detailed study.

Keywords Flat Slab, Structural Walls, Diaphragm Flexibility, Maximum Interstorey Drift.

Introduction

Flat slab buildings are more advantageous due to their architectural flexibility, greater space, simple formwork, and shorter duration of construction (Fig. 1). But these buildings show poor performance from past earthquakes that evidenced brittle failure; they lack sufficient lateral resistance offered by deep beams and structure walls. It induces huge deformation demands and causes damage to non-structural elements. It is necessary to examine the vulnerability of this building [Erberik and Elnashai, 2003]. Usually, massive shear forces and unbalanced bending moments are generated near the slab-to-column connections; this causes brittle punching shear failure. It shall be avoided by providing drop panels near the column head; it may reduce the shear demand and cannot ensure sufficient deformability under earthquake effects. Also, these drop panels cannot provide adequate resistance for punching shear during huge reversals of stresses [Megally and Ghali, 2000]. For example, punching shear failure of slab to column connection causing pan cake failure of entire car parking buildings during 2011 Christchurch earthquake. Thus, the entire flat slab behaviour is decided by the slab-column connection [Drakatos, 2016]. Also, based on the history of buildings that failed in Mexico City from past earthquakes, almost 47.2% of RC buildings were flat slab buildings [Reinoso et. al., 2021]. The punching shear resistance shall be enhanced by increasing the deformation capacity of flat slab building including gravity shear ratio, slab thickness, size of column, quantity of flexural reinforcement and slenderness of slab [Muttoni et. al., 2022]. The performance of flat slab buildings shall be enhanced by providing beams in the perimeter of the building and structural walls [Apostolska, 2008]. Otherwise, a few suggested to retrofit the flat slab buildings together with the structural walls by providing RC column jacketing and confining the plastic hinge regions with externally bonded steel plates [Hueste and Bai, 2007]. The performance of flat slab building should be experimentally tested with real full-scale models [Coronelli et. al., 2021]. IS 1893-1 involved three features to enhance the performance of flat slab buildings, including (i) RC structural walls (designed for 100% lateral load), (ii) perimeter RC special moment resisting frames (designed for 25% lateral load), and (if possible) an outrigger and belt truss system joining core structural walls and perimeter RC frames. Hence, an attempt is made to understand the features of a flat slab building, including perimeter beams and structural walls, in comparison with conventional buildings using elastic analyses. Also, the presence of a flat slab increases in-plane diaphragm flexibility, especially based on the location of structural walls, but it has seldom been considered in past studies. Therefore, the effect of diaphragm flexibility is studied by including and without including the effect of floor diaphragms.

Fig. 1. Typical flat slab building construction [Jasar, 2018]

Fig. 2. Failure of a flat slab building for car parking due to punching shear during the 2011 Christchurch earthquake, leading to the pancake collapse [Drakatos, 2016]

Numerical Study

A spectrum of building configurations (BC) is considered, including conventional and flat slab buildings. The elastic behaviour of buildings is studied using Modal Analysis MA and Equivalent Static Analysis ESA using ETABS software. The response parameters considered include (i) the distribution of hogging and sagging moments in the slab under gravity and lateral loads; (ii) diaphragm flexibility; (iii) maximum interstorey drift; (iv) storey shear; (v) the modal mass participation ratio and natural period; and (vi) base shear. Finally, the need for inelastic behaviour is demonstrated through a conventional slab building.

Building Configurations

Five different configurations considered in this study includes (i) conventional buildings (named as CB which is a conventional slab buildings having moment frames), (ii) Flat slab Building (named as FB which is a simple flat slab building without any beams), (iii) Flat slab with Perimeter Beam Building (named as FPBB which is a flat slab building provided with perimeter beams all around), (iv) Flat slab with Structural Wall Building (named as FSWB which is a flat slab building provided with structural walls in the periphery), and (v) Flat slab with Structural Wall and Perimeter Beam Building (named as FSWPBB which is a flat slab building provided with structural walls and perimeter beams all around) (Fig. 3). The thickness of slab for flat slab building calculated based on IS 456 is 200 mm; hence, it is also used for the conventional slab building. The columns in flat slab buildings are provided with drop panels to enhance the shear resistance. The rectangular plan dimension of the drop panel is around 1.3 m in each direction (taken as 1/3 of the panel length as per IS 456, 2000), and the thickness is 50 mm (1/4 the thickness of the slab). All buildings are 5-storey tall and have the same plan configuration with 5 bays in the X direction and 3 bays in the Y direction. The bay length is 4 m in each direction and has a 3 m storey height (a total height of 15 m). The sizes of beams, columns, and structural walls are uniform along height. The sizes of beams in all buildings (where applicable) are 300 mm × 400 mm, and the sizes of columns are 500 mm × 500 mm. The thickness of structural walls is taken as 150 mm. The stiffness modifiers used for beams and columns are 0.35 and 0.7, respectively. Infill wall thickness of 250 mm is used with a unit weight of 20 kN/m³. Also, a parapet wall of 1 m in height is considered at the roof top. The magnitude of loads from floor finish, live load, and roof live load are 1 kN/m², 3 kN/m², and 1.5 kN/m², respectively. M30 grade concrete and Fe 415 grade steel reinforcement is used. Lateral loads are estimated using IS 1893-1 for seismic zone V with hard rock-type soil having a response reduction factor of $R = 3$ and an importance factor of $I = 1$. With uniform mass distribution, the study is conducted with and without the rigid floor diaphragms. Natural periods (0.30s in X-direction and 0.39s in Y-direction) estimated from code are used for conducting the ESA in all buildings [IS 1893-1, 2016].

Fig. 3. Plan of building configurations of (i) CB, (ii) FB, (iii) FPBB, (iv) FSWB, and (v) FSWPBB

Elastic Behaviour

The elastic behaviour of all buildings is studied using responses from MA and ESA. The effect of floor diaphragms highly influences the behaviour of buildings under earthquake shaking. Although it is expected to behave rigidly, in a few cases, it behaves more like a flexible diaphragm due to the relative stiffness provided by the structural walls and their locations. Therefore, all the building's behaviour is studied without (WoD) and with (WD) diaphragms. While modelling the slabs in buildings WD, the constraint of rigid diaphragm is assigned, and for buildings WoD, the constraint of diaphragm rigidity is not assigned. Lastly, the responses studied in the understanding of elastic behaviour (in X- and Y-directions) include: (a) natural periods (T_x and T_y), (b) mass participation ratio (MP_x and MP_y), (c) base shear (V_x and V_y), (d) sagging and hogging bending moment distributions in slab, (e) normalised in-plane displacement of slab (Δ_n), (f) maximum interstorey drift along height (Δ_i), and (g) storey shear along height (V_s).

Dynamic Characteristics of Buildings and Base Shear

The dynamic characteristics like natural periods and modal mass participation ratios obtained from MA and base shear from ESA are obtained for all buildings, as shown in Table 1. The natural period estimated from MA does not match the code-calculated natural periods ($T_x = 0.3$ s and $T_y = 0.39$ s) for buildings without structural walls (e.g., CB, FB, and FPBB). But it almost matches the buildings with structural walls (e.g., FSWB and FSWPBB); therefore, code calculated natural periods are used in the ESA. Almost $\geq 80\%$ mass participation is noticed in CB, FB, and FPBB in both directions, but $\sim 73\%$ is obtained in FSWB and FSWPBB. Thus, almost good mass participation is obtained in all buildings. Observations remain the same for buildings WD and WoD. Almost similar base shear and observations are made in X- and Y-directions. FB and FPBB show less base shear than CB due to their flexibility. The provision of structural walls in FSWB and FSWPBB increases the base shear due to their increased lateral stiffness. It is more pronounced in buildings WD than WoD. CB shows the same base shear as WD or WOD; thus, the effect of WD or WOD is the same in CB. But WoD causes less base shear in FSWPBB but more base shear in WD. Thus, designing these buildings considering complete diaphragm actions may not ensure the building to exactly behave as WD. The effect of diaphragm flexibility must also be considered in buildings with structural walls.

Table 1. Characteristics of BCs from MA and ESA

Diaphragm	BC	T_x (s)	T_y (s)	MP_x (%)	MP_y (%)	V_x (kN)	V_y (kN)
WoD	CB	0.796	0.804	81.8	81.6	2856	2856
	FB	0.912	0.925	80.3	80.1	2674	2674
	FPBB	0.982	1.051	79.4	78.6	2559	2559
	FSWB	0.372	0.378	73.0	72.9	2796	2796
	FSWPBB	0.374	0.376	72.6	72.6	2681	2681
WD	CB	0.796	0.804	81.8	81.6	2856	2856
	FB	0.912	0.925	80.3	80.1	2674	2674
	FPBB	0.982	1.050	79.4	78.6	2559	2559
	FSWB	0.373	0.378	72.8	72.6	2806	2806
	FSWPBB	0.394	0.395	72.7	72.7	3117	3117

Bending Moment Distribution in Slab

The bending moment (BM) distribution is obtained along X- and Y-directions, considering the third-storey of the buildings (Table 2). M11 represents the BM about the Y-axis and M22 about the X-axis. Under gravity loading, CB shows a conventional two-way slab distribution with maximum sagging at the centre and hogging near the support regions. A similar observation is made in other flat slab buildings. But the magnitude of BM increased in FB due to the absence of beams. The presence of peripheral beams alone increases the BM, but with the presence of structural walls, the BM in the slab is reduced. Similarly, under lateral load effects (EQX and EQY), slabs show alternate sagging and hogging in each span. FB and FPBB show more BM in flat slab buildings. But the presence of structural walls reduces the BM in flat slab buildings. Similar observations are made in buildings WD and WoD. Thus, it is necessary to provide structural walls and periphery beams to reduce the demand imposed on flat slab buildings.

Normalised In-plane Displacement of Slab

The in-plane displacement is obtained at the roof top, and it is normalised with the edge displacement, Δ_n (Fig. 4). Buildings WD show the same in-plane displacements. But it is evident that the presence of structural walls increases the floor flexibility in buildings WoD. Though the magnitude of amplification is only 10%, an increase in the span length and location of structural walls will increase the displacement. Therefore, while providing structural walls in flat slab buildings, it is necessary to consider both the influence of rigid and flexible diaphragms to avoid adverse effects on buildings under earthquake effects (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Normalized in-plane deformation of the slab along the length of the building (L) under EQY

Maximum Interstorey Drift Along height

Maximum interstorey Δ_i is obtained along the height of buildings under lateral load effects in X- and Y-directions (Fig. 5). The drift is restricted within 0.4% of the height of buildings in CB (IS 1893-1). But with similar configurations, FB and FPBB show more displacements; the buildings become more flexible. It is necessary to stiffen the buildings with structural walls to ensure sufficient lateral stiffness in both directions, including perimeter beams. Similar observations are made in buildings WD and WoD.

Storey Shear along Height

The storey shear distribution along the height of the building for lateral load effects along X- and Y-directions. The storey shear distribution is like the base shear distribution (Table 1), with more in buildings WD and less in buildings WoD. Since all the buildings have almost the same base shear, the storey shear distribution almost remains the same in buildings WD. But, in buildings with WD, FSWPBB shows almost more storey shear than CB and FB, which show lesser storey shear. The force distribution changes with the diaphragm's rigidity. As a conservative estimate for lateral strength, buildings with WD shall be considered.

Table 2. Hogging and sagging moment distribution in slabs under ESA

(a) WoD

(b) WD

Fig. 5. Maximum interstorey drift along the height of the building

(a) WoD

Fig. 6. Storey shear distribution along the height of the building

Need for Inelastic Behaviour

Responses from elastic analyses show the importance of providing structural walls and beams on the periphery of flat slab buildings. But the poor performance of these buildings from past earthquakes evidenced a complete pancake collapse. Therefore, it is required to study the inelastic behaviour of buildings, including conventional and flat slabs, using nonlinear analysis. But studies conducted so far do not explicitly consider the modelling of slabs. Therefore, to demonstrate the importance of studying the inelastic behaviour of buildings, including slabs, CB is considered. Nonlinear static analysis (NLPoA) is performed using SAP 2000 on two different buildings: (i) a CB modelled including a nonlinear layered shell element for the slab, and (ii) a bare frame (BF) building of the CB without including the slab. Buildings are designed and detailed as per IS 456 and IS 13920. Autogenerated M3 hinges for beams and P-M2-M3 hinges for columns are assigned at the face of each element. The capacity curve (*lateral strength V versus roof displacement Δ_{roof}*) obtained in X- and Y-directions is obtained using NLPoA (Fig. 7). The lateral stiffness and strength of CB, including the slab, are higher than those of BF, but the deformability is reduced. Also, the addition of slabs causes poor energy dissipation, causing column sway mechanisms, but BF shows good energy dissipation mechanisms and collapse mechanisms. Thus, it is more important to explore inelastic analyses, including slabs.

Fig. 7. Capacity curve obtained from NLPoA, including their collapse mechanism

Conclusions

Buildings with flat slabs evidenced brittle collapse from past earthquakes. Therefore, the lateral resistance is enhanced in IS 1893-1 by including structural walls and peripheral beams in flat slab buildings and reducing the response reduction factor. Elastic behaviour of flat slabs and conventional buildings is studied using modal and equivalent static analyses with and without rigid diaphragm constraints. Responses studied include natural period, mass participation ratio, base shear, bending moment distribution in slabs, diaphragm flexibility, interstorey drift, and storey shear. The provision of structural walls reduces the huge bending moments induced in flat slab buildings. Also, maximum sagging and hogging bending moments are produced near the column head; hence, it causes more susceptibility to punching shear failure near column heads under huge stress reversals, as evidenced in the past. Also, buildings with rigid diaphragms attract more shear force, so they should be designed for higher forces. But the presence of structural walls causes floor flexibility and requires the displacement to be within the code-specified ranges. Demonstrating inelastic analysis, including slabs, causes poor collapse mechanisms and poor energy dissipation capacity. It is necessary to understand the behavior of flat slab buildings, including inelastic analysis.

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